

IMPROVEMENT OF DIAGNOSIS, DIAGNOSIS, AND TREATMENT METHODS OF DIZZINESS IN NEUROLOGY

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Abstract. *Dizziness is a clinical symptom of many somatic diseases and is one of the important symptoms of neurological diseases. The occurrence of dizziness in patients occurs as a result of injuries to various parts of the brain. Identifying the causes of dizziness and its adequate treatment leads to an improvement in the general condition of patients and a decrease in the complications of the disease.*

Keywords: *dizziness, brain, stroke, insecurity, neurorinitis, labyrinthitis.*

Introduction. Dizziness is a condition in which there is a sensation of movement in space of the human body or surrounding objects. This symptom can also be defined as an illusion of movement, because objectively the human body and surrounding objects are in a stationary state (not in motion). Usually, patients go to the doctor, formulating this symptom as follows - "the earth is spinning", "everything around is spinning", "losing ground under your feet". Often patients describe this sensation as weakness, fatigue, a feeling of insecurity, so it is very important to determine exactly what the person actually feels and what it is associated with.

Acute spontaneous dizziness can be a symptom of numerous and very different diseases. These diseases have one common feature – sudden damage to the vestibular system or its connections with other parts of the brain. Diseases that lead to acute dizziness can affect the peripheral part of the vestibular analyzer (for example, the labyrinth of the inner ear or the vestibular nerve) or those components of the vestibular system that are located in the central nervous system, primarily in the brainstem, or have connections with the cerebellum. From a practical point of view, the most difficult is the differential diagnosis of acute, first-time vestibular dizziness, since recurrent and reversible dizziness in the overwhelming majority of cases is associated with more or less benign diseases of the peripheral part of the vestibular analyzer and is extremely rarely a consequence of repeated transient ischemic attacks or other diseases of the central nervous system.

Methodology. Among the most common causes of acute, new-onset, non-recurrent dizziness are vestibular neuronitis and vertebrobasilar stroke. Vestibular neuronitis is associated with selective inflammation of the vestibular nerve [2]. The inflammation is thought to be caused by herpes simplex virus type 1 [3]. Vestibular neuronitis presents with a sudden and prolonged attack of systemic dizziness, accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and imbalance. The disease may be preceded by a respiratory viral infection. Sometimes, several hours or days before the development of an acute vestibular attack, patients experience short-term episodes of dizziness or instability. Symptoms of vestibular neuronitis increase with head movements or changes in body position, but, unlike benign paroxysmal positional vertigo, do not go away at rest. Dizziness may be reduced by fixing the gaze. Neurological examination reveals no symptoms of damage to the brainstem or other parts of the brain. Hearing does not decrease with vestibular neuronitis. In cases

where sensorineural hearing loss develops simultaneously with dizziness, labyrinthitis is diagnosed [4]. The duration of dizziness ranges from several hours to several days.

After the dizziness has ceased, patients continue to experience instability for several days or weeks. Then, thanks to the mechanisms of central vestibular compensation, instability also regresses. Vestibular neuronitis relapses relatively rarely: according to various data, in 1.9–10.7% of cases [5, 6]. Another, rarer, but also much more formidable cause of an attack of vestibular dizziness that has arisen for the first time may be a stroke in the vertebrobasilar system. About 20% of ischemic strokes are caused by a stroke in the vertebrobasilar system, and one of the main manifestations of such a stroke is dizziness [7]. Dizziness during a stroke may be one of the symptoms of the disease or its only manifestation. In the first case, diagnosing a stroke for a neurologist is usually not difficult. Among infarctions in the vertebrobasilar system, accompanied by dizziness as one of the symptoms, the most common is an infarction of the dorsolateral part of the medulla oblongata and the lower surface of the cerebellar hemisphere, which occurs due to occlusion of the vertebral or posterior inferior cerebellar artery.

It manifests itself as Wallenberg-Zakharchenko syndrome, which in its classic form includes dizziness, nausea, vomiting; on the side of the lesion - pain and temperature hypesthesia of the face, cerebellar ataxia, Horner's syndrome, paralysis of the pharynx, larynx and palate, leading to dysphagia and dysphonia; on the opposite side - pain and temperature hemihypesthesia. Variants of this syndrome are often observed, which manifest themselves mainly as dizziness, nystagmus and cerebellar ataxia [8, 9].

The second most common variant of ischemic stroke in the vertebrobasilar system, manifested by non-isolated dizziness, is caused by blockage of the anterior inferior cerebellar artery. In this case, in addition to dizziness, the following disorders are usually observed: ipsilateral paresis of the facial muscles and hearing loss, paresis of gaze towards the lesion; contralateral decrease in pain and temperature sensitivity. In addition, nystagmus, tinnitus, cerebellar ataxia, and Horner's syndrome are characteristic.

Occlusion of the initial part of the artery may be accompanied by damage to the corticospinal tract and, consequently, hemiparesis. Isolated vertigo as a symptom of stroke is much less common. A recent large population study [8] showed that stroke accounts for only 0.7% of cases of isolated vestibular vertigo. However, according to other data [6], 62% of patients with stroke in the vertebrobasilar system had previously experienced at least one episode of vestibular vertigo, and in 19% of those examined, vertigo was the first symptom of stroke, which was later joined by other manifestations of brainstem or cerebellar ischemia.

Another recent study [5] showed that patients hospitalized for acute dizziness have a 2-fold higher risk of all acute cardiovascular events over the next 3 years than the general population. It was noted that patients hospitalized for acute dizziness have a 3-fold higher risk of stroke over the next 4 years than the general population [4,5]. Thus, the relationship between cerebrovascular pathology and dizziness is still poorly understood and requires further research, and isolated dizziness may be a more common manifestation of cerebral ischemia, especially in high-risk groups for cerebrovascular disease. The anatomical substrate of isolated dizziness in cerebrovascular diseases includes selective damage to the cerebellar nodule (this area is supplied with blood by the medial branch of the posterior inferior cerebellar artery), the cerebellar flocculus, the brainstem area in the region of the vestibular nerve root entry, and the vestibular nuclei.

There are few descriptions of isolated vestibular dizziness that occurs when brain structures outside the brainstem and cerebellum are damaged. Thus, acute isolated dizziness has been described in infarctions in the region of the insular lobe and the left parietal lobe with spread to the region of the supramarginal gyrus [1,3]. Moreover, in these cases, dizziness could be accompanied by horizontal nystagmus.

In cases where a stroke leads to the formation of persistent vestibular dysfunction manifested by nystagmus, symptomatic agents are used to reduce oscillopsia and instability [2,3]. Thus, with downward nystagmus caused by ischemia of the lower parts of the brainstem or bilateral damage to the flocculent zone of the cerebellum, baclofen at a dose of 5 mg 3 times a day or clonazepam at a dose of 0.5 mg 3 times a day can be effective. With a stroke with damage to the medial parts of the medulla oblongata or pontomesencephalic region, upward nystagmus occurs.

This nystagmus is rarely persistent, and therefore treatment is usually not required. If it does lead to prolonged oscillopsia, baclofen is prescribed at a dose of 5–10 mg 3 times a day. Stroke with damage to the pons and medulla oblongata can lead to the formation of acquired pendulum nystagmus. In such cases, memantine is used at 10 mg 4 times a day or gabapentin at 300 mg 4 times a day [2,4]. The advisability of the widespread use of vasoactive and nootropic drugs in the treatment of patients with dizziness due to stroke is questionable. However, some medications, according to the results of controlled studies, are able to reduce the severity of instability in this category of patients. One of these drugs is nicergoline (sermion). The therapeutic effectiveness of the drug is due to the alpha-adrenoblocking effect and direct influence on the neurotransmitter systems - noradrenergic, dopaminergic and acetylcholinergic.

Results and discussion. According to the results of a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study, the use of nicergoline at a dose of 60 mg/day for 3 months in patients with instability caused by damage to the central parts of the vestibular analyzer led to a significant improvement in the condition according to the results of the Dizziness Handicap Inventory (DHI) and the Dizziness Assessment Rating Scale (DARS).

An important component of treating a patient with dizziness caused by a stroke is vestibular rehabilitation. Vestibular rehabilitation in patients who have suffered a stroke is less effective than in peripheral vestibular disorders. This is due to the fact that full vestibular adaptation requires the preservation of the cerebellum and its connections with the vestibular system, since it is the cerebellum that provides a modulating effect on the vestibulo-ocular reflex and promotes vestibular compensation. Meanwhile, it is the cerebellum that is often damaged in strokes accompanied by dizziness. Despite this, vestibular rehabilitation in patients who have had a stroke reduces the risk of falls and improves quality of life. Thus, the examination of a patient with acute, first-time dizziness should always be aimed at excluding stroke as a possible cause of vestibular dysfunction.

Dizziness in stroke is usually accompanied by other focal neurological symptoms, but in some cases it can be isolated. Differential diagnostics using anamnesis data, clinical neurovestibular and neurological examination, MRI of the brain is effective in most cases and allows timely differentiation of dizziness caused by stroke from dizziness in peripheral vestibular disorders.

Conclusions. Dizziness syndrome is one of the main symptoms of many neurological diseases and other somatic diseases. In this case, it is important to conduct differential diagnostics

using MRI of the brain, CT examination, as well as clinical neurological examination and other instrumental studies. ENT specialists should check the vestibular function and exclude inflammatory diseases of the inner ear. In neurological diseases, dizziness is accompanied by nystagmus, nausea and vomiting. Standard neurological treatment leads to an improvement in the condition of patients.

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